

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Турсуной Эргашева

ХАЛҚАРО СОЛИҚ ХУЖЖАТЛАРИНИ ХАЛҚАРО АЛМАШИНУВИНИ

ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ВА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ

DRJI

 Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

 ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ